

Computerized Disease Vector Identification Keys¹

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Abstract

An illustrated, interactive, computerized key to the mosquito genera of North America is presented. The key assists military preventive medicine personnel in assessing the threat from arthropod-borne disease, allowing them to develop successful, cost-effective, and environmentally safe countermeasures. The software is designed for use by military preventive medicine personnel and demonstrates how information currently available only in printed format can be adapted and improved for use with computer systems. Data and directive files for the key are formatted for use with the DELTA system of programs and the key implements a beta version of INTKEY 4.0.

1: Introduction

Identification of disease-transmitting arthropods is a basic preventive medicine skill. It is necessary in order to assess the risk to troops of arthropod-borne diseases, and to develop adequate, cost-effective, and environmentally sound control strategies. Unfortunately, arthropod identification is a difficult skill to master. As a result, entomological support for deployments is greatly diminished. Unless this situation is reversed, increased military deployments to underdeveloped regions will result in increased risk of arthropod-borne disease among the deployed troops.

Now, as in the past, written keys provide the basis for vector identification. Written keys have many drawbacks. They are cumbersome, inflexible, and difficult to use, especially for first-time users. Written keys are difficult to produce and therefore tend to lack much needed ancillary information such as bionomics, medical importance, and recommended control strategies for the identified arthropod. Because keys take so long to produce, they cannot be upgraded to reflect recent changes in our

knowledge. As a result, written keys are always out of date. Keys are seldom written for large taxonomic groups or to cover large geographic areas, and certainly never for both. Written keys are summaries of an expert's knowledge. Unfortunately, this knowledge is presented in a form that is useful only to other experts. When present, figures tend to be diagrammatic and in black and white. Inexperienced users are unable to make the anatomical association between the diagrams and the actual specimens. Furthermore, many key identification features are based on differences in color which often cannot be illustrated in black and white.

Computers provide the perfect medium for identification keys. Instead of merely digitizing existing keys and placing them on magnetic media, we can develop entirely new ways of presenting and using those keys. This approach overcomes all the problems experienced with written keys. For example, even a very large key or a number of large keys can fit onto a very small, portable computer. Interactivity built into the keys allows users to begin the identification process with any character. This approach allows the user to make an identification even if some of the structures are missing from their specimen. Important ancillary data, such as bionomics or medical importance of the identified arthropod, can be presented automatically and through interactive links. The interactive key can be updated and expanded constantly so that they are always up to date. New technologies for arthropod and disease agent identification, such as RAPD PCR and other molecular and immunological techniques, can be integrated into the keys for maximum utility.

2: Product description

The Key to the Mosquito Genera of North America is designed for training Preventive Medicine Technicians and Military Entomologists at the U.S. Army Medical Department Center & School. The key is also of use to Center for Health Promotion and Preventive Medicine

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(CHPPM) activities and Medical Department Activities (MEDDAC) in the United States. An expanded key currently under development, Key to the Mosquito Genera of the World, is designed for use by all field units tasked with performing vector identification and will have applications in all military contingency operations as well as CHPPM activities around the world.

The key was developed using the DELTA [1] (DEscription Language for TAXonomy) programming environment. It uses the beta version of INTKEY [2] Version 4.0, but also works with the MS-DOS® version of INTKEY. INTKEY 4.0 requires Microsoft® Windows™ 3.1 and any hardware capable of running Windows. A non-interlaced display and a super VGA display card with Windows accelerator is recommended. The Interactive Key to North American Mosquito Genera occupies less than 5 MB of hard disk space.

The key makes maximum use of color images. The images are stored as Graphics Interchange Format (GIF) files. Most of the graphics files contain captured video images from actual specimens, making the key unique, even among computerized keys. There are over 60 color images arranged into 28 GIF files to guide the user through the identification process. Two GIF files provide reference figures for locating morphological structures. Thirty-two GIF files provide images of the identified mosquitoes, as well as information on their distribution, bionomics, and medical importance. Seven GIF files also provide information on the distribution, cycle of transmission, vectors, and description of disease for the major North American arboviruses as well as malaria.

3: Conclusion

This software serves the field preventive medicine specialist as part of an integrated approach to the

identification and management of the arthropod-borne disease threat. Our goal is to conserve the fighting strength for commanders by reducing the number of disease and non-battle injuries due to arthropod-borne disease.

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5: References

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